

Network hermeneutics: exploring the meaning of a source using network analysis, case of inquisitorial protocols from 14th century Stettin

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Hermeneutics, the art of nuanced interpretation of text, is the cornerstone method within historical studies. Its meaning has taken on new dimensions with the development of digital technologies, leading to the emergence of 'digital hermeneutics' and related concepts e.g digital source criticism (e.g Mallery et al. 1986; Fickers 2020; Romele et al. 2020). This paper explores digital source criticism not just as a means to interpret digital representations of sources but as an approach to uncovering the context and creation processes behind historical documents.

In the context of our case study we ask how the network structure of relational data derived from the textual source reflects on its nature and creation process. Can we use this knowledge to learn about the historical phenomena operating in the background and how they influence any quantitative analysis of the source? Employing statistical methods, particularly network analysis, we analyse complete data projections from the source.

With this, we add a new type of quantitative layer that can reveal patterns, connections, and structures within the texts that might not be apparent through conventional reading and analysis and hint at the context of the creation of the source.

The case study at the heart of this paper is the inquisition protocols from the 14th century, specifically the records of the Celestine inquisitor Petrus Zwicker from 1392 to 1394 in Stettin. These documents, central to understanding the Waldensian dissidence and the broader inquisitorial practices of the time, are reexamined through a digital lens. This analysis is based on a network form structured dataset created from the original sources, based on D. Kurze's regesta edition (1975). This data creation process followed the social network analysis (SNA) coding which involved close reading of the sources and documenting people, events, places and relations between them. The dataset was then converted into edge lists containing relations between specific entities.

We investigate the origin story of the source. Is it a document resulting from "live" inquisitional interrogations that evolved during the investigation, where new information influenced subsequent interrogations, or a pre-planned process devoid of such dynamism? For this, we study the inclusion of deponents in the trial process, did information leading to the interrogation of deponents originate from previous depositions? This question is not merely procedural but goes to the heart of understanding the nature of the source itself. The differentiation between a dynamic and a static interrogation process can lead to significantly different interpretations of the source and variations in the network model that can be derived from it.

To explore those variations we describe the evolutions of the evolving evidence network longitudinally, measuring its spatial and network characteristics as it evolves in time bearing the footprint of the intent behind the inquisitorial process.

The study's findings demonstrate how the creation process impacts the nature of the source giving its contents a different structure when converted to a complete digital form. It shows how "network hermeneutics" can contribute not only to our historical knowledge of the source but also frame the interpretation of any digital models derived from it. We aim to contribute to the critique of historical sources

and demonstrate that protocols are not just straightforward accounts of interrogations and show how they have been shaped by the institutional and procedural frameworks of the Inquisition. We discuss natural biases in the network structure within the text coming from its creation process and which opportunities and limits it creates for further quantitative analysis.

References

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